

A

Primer	5'-3' Sequence
LiDGAT1 _{opt} F-BamHI	AT <u>AGGATCC</u> ATGTCGGGCATGTCTGGC
LiDGAT1 _{optNS} R-XhoI	ATA <u>CTCGAGT</u> CACCGGTTGAGGACGCA
LiDGAT2.1 _{opt} F-BamHI	AT <u>AGGATCC</u> ATGGAATTGGCCTCAGCTAAG
LiDGAT2.1 _{optNS} R-SalI	ATAGT <u>CGACCT</u> CGATGATGTGCAGGCTG
LiDGAT2.2 _{opt} F-BamHI	AT <u>AGGATCC</u> ATGGCTTTGAGATGGTCTAGAGT
LiDGAT2.2 _{optNS} R-SalI	ATAGT <u>CGACCT</u> CGACCATGCGCAGCTC
LiDGAT2.3 _{opt} F-BamHI	AT <u>AGGATCC</u> ATGGCTCCATCTTTGGACTCT
LiDGAT2.3 _{optNS} R-SalI	ATAGT <u>CGACAGCC</u> ATGACGAGCTCCAC

OPT; codon optimized, NS; no stop codon.

Underlined - restriction sites.

B

Backbone	MCS1	MCS2	Reference
pEsc-Ura	Empty	Empty	Agilent technologies Cat no. 217454-51
pEsc-Ura	LiDGAT1 _{opt} -FLAG	Empty	<i>This work</i>
pEsc-Ura	Empty	LiDGAT2.1 _{opt} -myc	<i>This work</i>
pEsc-Ura	Empty	LiDGAT2.2 _{opt} -myc	<i>This work</i>
pEsc-Ura	Empty	LiDGAT2.3 _{opt} -myc	<i>This work</i>
pEsc-Ura	LiDGAT1 _{opt} -FLAG	LiDGAT2.2 _{opt} -myc	<i>This work</i>
pEsc-Ura	LiDGAT2.1 _{opt} -FLAG	LiDGAT2.2 _{opt} -myc	<i>This work</i>
pEsc-Ura	LiDGAT2.2 _{opt} -FLAG	LiDGAT2.3 _{opt} -myc	<i>This work</i>

MCS; multiple cloning site.